

ON b-SEPARATED M-SETS

B. Amudhambigai*, G. K. Revathi & Vaideshwari***

* Department of Mathematics, Sri Sarada College for Women (Autonomous),
Salem, Tamilnadu

** Mathematics Division, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University,
Chennai, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: B. Amudhambigai, G. K. Revathi & Vaideshwari, "On b-Separated M-Sets", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 218-220, 2017.

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Abstract:

In this chapter the concepts of b-open M-sets, b-closed M-sets and b-separated M-sets are studied. Also, some of their properties and characterizations are discussed.

Key Words: b-open M-sets, b-closed M-sets & b-separated M-sets

1. Introduction:

Since then the introduction of M-topological spaces by Gitish and Sunil Jacob [6], various authors [1,2 and 6] studied the many interesting topological properties in M- topological spaces. Andrijevic [3] studied b-open sets. EI-Atik A A et al[4]. Studied the applications of b-connectedness. In this article, the concept of b-open M-sets, b-closed M-sets and b-separated M-sets are studied. Also, some of their properties and characterizations are discussed.

2. Preliminaries:

Definition 2.1 [6]: An M-set M drawn from the set X is represented by a function Count M or C_M defined as $C_M : X \rightarrow W$ where W represents the set of whole numbers. Here is $C_M(x)$ the number of occurrences of the element x in the M-set M. We represent the M-set M drawn from the set $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ as

$$M = \left\{ \begin{matrix} m_1 & m_2 & \dots & m_n \\ x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \end{matrix} \right\} \text{ where } m_i \text{ is the number of occurrences of the element } x_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ in the M-set M.}$$

Those elements which are not included in the M-set have zero count. Since the count of each element in an M-set is always a non-negative integer so, W is taken as the range space instead of N.

Definition 2.2 [6]: Let $M \in [X]^W$ and $\tau \subseteq P^*(M)$. Then τ is called a Multiset topology of M if τ satisfies the following properties.

- ✓ The M-set M and the empty M-set ϕ are in τ .
- ✓ The M-set union of the elements of any sub collection of τ is in τ .
- ✓ The M-set intersection of the elements of any finite sub collection of τ is in τ .

Definition 2.3 [1]: A subset A of a Topological space (X, τ) is called a b-open set if $A \subseteq \text{cl}(\text{int}(A)) \cup \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$.

3. On b-Separated M-Sets:

Throughout this chapter X denotes a non-empty set and $C_M: X \rightarrow W$ where W represents the set of whole numbers.

Definition 3.1: Let (M, τ) be an M-topological space. Any sub M-set A of M is said to be a b-open M-set if $A \subseteq \text{cl}(\text{int}(A)) \cup \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$ with $C_A(x) \leq C_{\text{cl}(\text{int}(A)) \cup \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))}(x)$, for all $x \in X$. The collection of all b-open M-sets in (M, τ) is denoted $\text{BO}(M)$. The complement of a b-open M-set is a b-closed M-set.

Example 3.1: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $w = 2$ and $M = \{1/a, 1/b, 2/c\}$. Let $\tau = \{M, \phi, \{1/a\}, \{1/b\}, \{1/a, 1/b\}\}$. Then τ is an M-topology and (M, τ) is an M-topological space. Also $\tau^c = \{\phi, M, \{1/a, 2/c\}, \{1/b, 2/c\}, \{2/c\}\}$. Let $A = \{1/a\}$. Clearly, $A \subseteq \text{cl}(\text{int}(A)) \cup \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$ and $C_A(x) \leq C_{\text{cl}(\text{int}(A)) \cup \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))}(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Hence $A = \{1/a\}$ is a b-open M-set.

Example 3.2: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $w = 2$ and $M = \{1/a, 2/b, 1/c\}$. Then τ is an M-topology and (M, τ) is an M-topological space. Also $\tau^c = \{\phi, M, \{2/b, 1/c\}, \{1/a, 2/b\}, \{2/b\}\}$. Let $A = \{1/a, 1/b\}$. Clearly, $\text{int}(\text{cl}(A)) \cap \text{cl}(\text{int}(A)) \subseteq A$ and $C_{\text{int}(\text{cl}(A)) \cap \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))}(x) \leq C_A(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Hence $A = \{1/a, 1/b\}$ is a b-closed M-set.

Definition 3.2: Let (M, τ) be an M-topological space and A be any sub M-set of M. The b-closure of A and b-interior of A respectively denoted and defined by $\text{bcl}(A) = \cap \{B : B \supseteq A, \text{ each } B \subseteq M \text{ is a b-open M-set}\}$ with $C_{\text{bcl}(A)}(x) = \min \{C_B(x) : B \supseteq A \text{ each } B \subseteq M \text{ is a b-open M-set}\}$, for all $x \in X$. $\text{bint}(A) = \cup \{B : B \subseteq A, \text{ each } B \subseteq M \text{ is a b-closed M-set}\}$ with $C_{\text{bint}(A)}(x) = \max \{C_B(x) : B \subseteq A \text{ each } B \subseteq M \text{ is a b-closed M-set}\}$, for all $x \in X$.

Example 3.3: Let $X = \{ a, b, c \}$, $w = 2$ and $M = \{ 1/a, 2/b, 1/c \}$. Then τ is an M -topology and (M, τ) is an M -topological space. Also $\tau^c = \{ \phi, M, \{ 1/a, 2/b \}, \{ 2/b, 1/c \}, \{ 2/b \} \}$. The collection of all b -open M -sets is $\{ \{ M, \phi, \{ 2/b, 1/c \}, \{ 1/a, 2/b \}, \{ 1/b, 1/c \}, \{ 1/c \}, \{ 1/a, 1/b \}, \{ 1/a \} \}$. Let $A = \{ 1/b \}$ be a sub M -set of M . Then $\text{bint}(A) = \phi$ with $C_{\text{bint}(A)}(x) = \max \{ C_B(x) : B \subseteq A \text{ each } B \subseteq M \text{ is a } b\text{-open } M\text{-set} \}$, for all $x \in X$. The collection of all b -closed M -sets is $\{ \phi, M, \{ 1/a \}, \{ 1/c \}, \{ 1/a, 1/b \}, \{ 1/a, 2/b \}, \{ 1/b, 1/c \}, \{ 2/b, 1/c \} \}$. Let $A = \{ 1/a, 2/b \}$ be a sub M -set of M . Then $\text{bcl}(A) = \{ 1/a, 2/b \}$ with $C_{\text{bcl}(A)}(x) = \min \{ C_B(x) : B \supseteq A \text{ each } B \subseteq M \text{ is a } b\text{-closed } M\text{-set} \}$, for all $x \in X$.

Definition 3.3: Any M -topological space (M, τ) is said to be a b -connected M -space if M cannot be expressed as the union of two disjoint nonempty b -open M -sets of M .

Definition 3.4: Let (M, τ) be an M -topological space. Any sub M -set $A \subseteq M$ is called a b -neighborhood M -set of a point $x \in {}^m M$ if there exists a b -open M -set $U \subseteq A$ such that $x \in {}^m U \subseteq A$ with $C_{\{m/x\}} \leq C_{U(x)} \leq C_{A(x)}$, for all $x \in X$.

Definition 3.5: Let (M, τ) be an M -topological space. Two sub M -sets A and B of M are said to be b -separated M -set if and only if $A \cap \text{bcl}(B) = \phi$ with $C_{A \cap \text{bcl}(B)}(x) = 0$ and $\text{bcl}(A) \cap B = \phi$ with $C_{\text{bcl}(A) \cap B}(x) = 0$, for all $x \in X$.

Example 3.4: Let $X = \{ a, b, c \}$, $w = 2$ and $M = \{ 1/a, 1/b, 2/c \}$. Let $\tau = \{ M, \phi, \{ 1/a \}, \{ 1/b \}, \{ 1/a, 1/b \} \}$. Then τ is an M -topology and (M, τ) is an M -topological space. Also $\tau^c = \{ \phi, M, \{ 1/a, 2/c \}, \{ 1/b, 2/c \}, \{ 2/c \} \}$. The collection of all b -open M -sets is $\{ \{ 1/a \}, \{ 1/b \}, \{ 1/a, 1/b \}, \{ 1/a, 1/c \}, \{ 1/a, 2/c \}, \{ 1/b, 1/c \}, \{ 1/b, 2/c \}, \{ 1/a, 1/b, 1/c \} \}$. Hence the collection of all b -closed M -sets is $\{ \{ M, \phi, \{ 1/b, 2/c \}, \{ 1/a, 2/c \}, \{ 2/c \}, \{ 1/b, 1/c \}, \{ 1/b \}, \{ 1/a, 1/c \}, \{ 1/a \} \}$. Let $A = \{ 1/a \}$ and $B = \{ 2/c \}$. Then, $\text{bcl}(B) = \{ 2/c \}$ with $C_{\text{bcl}(B)}(a) = 0$, $C_{\text{bcl}(B)}(b) = 0$, $C_{\text{bcl}(B)}(c) = 2$. Therefore, $A \cap \text{bcl}(B) = \{ 1/a \} \cap \{ 2/c \} = \phi$ with $C_{A \cap \text{bcl}(B)}(a) = 0$, $C_{A \cap \text{bcl}(B)}(b) = 0$, $C_{A \cap \text{bcl}(B)}(c) = 0$. Then $\text{bcl}(A) = \{ 1/a \}$ with $C_{\text{bcl}(A)}(a) = 1$, $C_{\text{bcl}(A)}(b) = 0$, $C_{\text{bcl}(A)}(c) = 0$ and $B = \{ 2/c \}$. But $\text{bcl}(A) \cap B = \{ 1/a \} \cap \{ 2/c \} = \phi$ with $C_{\text{bcl}(A) \cap B}(a) = 0$, $C_{\text{bcl}(A) \cap B}(b) = 0$, $C_{\text{bcl}(A) \cap B}(c) = 0$. Hence, A and B are b -Separated M -sets.

Proposition 3.1: Let (M, τ) be an M -topological space and A and B be any two nonempty sub M -sets of M . Then the following statements hold:

- ✓ For any two sub M -sets A_1 and B_1 of M , if A and B are b -Separated M -sets such that $A_1 \subseteq A$ with $C_{A_1}(x) \leq C_A(x)$, for all $x \in X$ and $B_1 \subseteq B$ with $C_{B_1}(x) \leq C_B(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Then A_1 and B_1 are also b -separated M -sets.
- ✓ If each of A and B are both b -closed M -sets and b -open M -sets such that, $A \cap B = \phi$ with $C_{A \cap B}(x) = 0$, for all $x \in X$, then A and B are b -separated M -sets.
- ✓ If each of A and B are both b -closed M -sets and b -open M -sets and if $H = A \cap (M \ominus B)$ with $C_H(x) = C_{A \cap (M \ominus B)}(x)$, for all $x \in X$ and $G = B \cap (M \ominus A)$ with $C_G(x) = C_{B \cap (M \ominus A)}(x)$, for all $x \in X$, then H and G are b -separated M -sets.

Proposition 3.2: Let (M, τ) be an M -topological space. The sub M -sets A and B of M are b -separated M -sets if and only if there exist U and V in $BO(M)$ such that $A \subseteq U$ with $C_A(x) \leq C_U(x)$, for all $x \in X$, $B \subseteq V$ with $C_B(x) \leq C_V(x)$, for all $x \in X$ and $A \cap V = \phi$ with $C_{A \cap V}(x) = 0$, for all $x \in X$, $B \cap U = \phi$ with $C_{B \cap U}(x) = 0$, for all $x \in X$.

Definition 3.6: Let (M, τ) be an M -topological space. Let A be any sub M -set of M . A point $x \in {}^m M$ is called a b -limit point of A if every b -open M -set $U \subseteq M$ with $C_U(x) < C_M(x)$ containing m/x contains a point of A other than m/x .

Proposition 3.3: Let (M, τ) be an M -topological space. Let A and B be any two nonempty disjoint sub M -sets of M and $E = A \cup B$ with $C_E(x) = C_{A \cup B}(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Then A and B are b -separated M -set if and only if each of A and B is nb -closed M -set (b -open M -set) in E .

Definition 3.7: Let (M, τ) be an M -topological space and A and B be any two sub M -sets. Any sub M -set S of M is said to be b -connected relative to M if there do not exist two b -separated sub M -sets A and B relative to M and $S = A \cup B$ with $C_S(x) = C_{A \cup B}(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Otherwise, S is said to be a b -disconnected M -set.

Proposition 3.4: Let (M, τ) be an M -topological space. Let E be any sub M -set of M . If E is a b -connected M -set, then $\text{bcl}(E)$ is a b -connected M -set.

Proposition 3.5: Let (M, τ) be an M -topological space. Let $A \subseteq B \cup C$ with $C_A(x) \leq C_{B \cup C}(x)$ such that A is a nonempty b -connected M -set in (M, τ) and B, C are b -separated M -sets. Then only one of the following conditions holds

- ✓ $A \subseteq B$ and $A \cap C = \phi$ with $C_A(x) \leq C_B(x)$ and $C_{A \cap C}(x) = 0$, for all $x \in X$.
- ✓ $A \subseteq C$ and $A \cap B = \phi$ with $C_A(x) \leq C_C(x)$ and $C_{A \cap B}(x) = 0$, for all $x \in X$.

Definition 3.8:

Let (M, τ_1) and (N, τ_2) be any two M-topological spaces. Then any M-set function $f : (M, \tau_1) \rightarrow (N, \tau_2)$ is said to be a

- ✓ b-continuous M-set function if for each b-open sub M-set V of N , the M-set $f^{-1}(V)$ is a b-open sub M-set of (M, τ_1)
- ✓ b-open M-set if the image of each open M-set in (M, τ_1) is a b-open M-set in (N, τ_2)
- ✓ b-closed M-set if the image of each closed M-set in (M, τ_1) is a b-closed M-set in (N, τ_2) .

Proposition 3.6: Let (M, τ_1) and (N, τ_2) be any two M-topological spaces. Let $f : (M, \tau_1) \rightarrow (N, \tau_2)$ be a b-continuous M-set function. Then $bcl(f^{-1}(B)) \subseteq f^{-1}(cl(B))$ with $C_{bcl(f^{-1}(B))} \leq C_{f^{-1}(cl(B))}$, for all $x \in X$ for each $B \subseteq Y$ with $C_B(x) \leq C_Y(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Proposition 3.7: Let (M, τ_1) and (N, τ_2) be any two M-topological spaces. Let $f : (M, \tau_1) \rightarrow (N, \tau_2)$ be a b-continuous M-set function. and if K is b-connected M-set in (M, τ_1) then $f(K)$ is a connected M-set in (N, τ_2) .

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